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Selection of components for demonstrations and measurement campaign

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Abstract

This deliverable discusses the selected system components, the physical deployment scenarios, as well as the scheduled measurement campaigns, enabling practical proof-of-concept (PoC) demonstrations of the innovative architecture, protocols, and algorithmic methods developed in the 6G-DISAC Project. In particular, it describes in detail five different demonstrators developed under work package 5 (WP5) with special focus on defining and justifying the selection of technologies, components, and methods, as well as planning for future measurement campaigns. The first four demonstrators focus on key technologies developed under WP2, WP3 and WP4, such as novel DISAC network architecture interfaces, semantic waveforms, distributed reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS)-based integrated sensing and communication (ISAC), as well as distributed channel sounding and waveform testing platform. The fifth demonstrator represents a multi-modal distributed sensing scenario that capitalizes on some of the Project's main technical solutions, thereby integrating different key technologies in a real-world assisted parking use case. These five demonstrations are intended to cover key segments and required functionalities of typical distributed ISAC systems (incl. acquisition, communication, and fusion of sensing data), while considering them independently, but also in a more combined fashion. Furthermore, this deliverable outlines relevant DISAC key performance indicators (KPIs) for performance assessment of such demonstrators, as outlined in WP2. This document ensures that subsequent measurements and evaluation work is aligned with the overall objectives of the Project.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC); Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication (DISAC); Proof-of-Concept (PoC); experimental validation; Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); Smart Factory; Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Protection; Semantic Communication; Wireless Communication Technologies.

Disclaimer

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

5G-NR	5G-New Radio
6G	Sixth-Generation
ADAS	Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems
AoA	Angle-of-Arrival
AoD	Angle-of-Departure
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BS	Base Station
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CSAS	Correlation-based Semantic-Aware Synchronization
CSePF	Centralised Sensing Processing Function
CTF	Channel Transfer Function
DISAC	Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication
DL	Downlink
DMA	Dynamic Metasurface Antenna
EFC	Edge Fusion Centre
FMCW	Frequency-Modulated Continuous Wave
FNN	Feed-Forward Network
FoV	Field of View
FR	Frequency Range
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
gNB	gNodeB
GNN	Graph Neural Network
HPBW	Half Power Beamwidth
HRIS	Hybrid Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
HW	Hardware
IMU	Inertia Measurement Unit
IRLS	Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
ISM	Industrial, Scientific, and Medical
IWT	Inverse Walsh Transform
KG	Knowledge Graph
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LS	Least Squares
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
MCU	Micro Controller Unit
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
mmWave	Millimetre Wave
MPC	Multipath Component
NLoS	Non-Line-of-Sight

OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OSSDM	Orthogonal Semantic Sequency Division Multiplexing
PADP	Power Angular-Delay Profile
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PoC	Proof of Concept
PRS	Positioning Reference Signals
RAN	Radio Access Network
RCS	Radar Cross Section
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RX	Receiver
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SFAR	Sparse Fourier Approximation Reconstruction
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SPU	Signal Processing Unit
SRx	Sensing Rx
ST	Sensing Target
STx	Sensing Tx
SW	Software
TDD	Time Division Duplexing
TR	Technical Report
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TX	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and Objectives

The transition toward sixth-generation (6G) wireless systems marks a profound transformation in network capabilities. Beyond the expected improvements in throughput, reliability, and latency, 6G aims to incorporate native support for functions such as environmental sensing and high-precision localization, alongside conventional communications. A key enabler of this vision is integrated sensing and communication (ISAC), which allows the radio interface to perform environmental sensing concurrently with data transmission [WQW+23], [LLL+24].

Despite its promise, the current ISAC landscape remains dominated by centralized, loosely coupled designs that address communication and sensing functionalities separately. Moreover, the latter is often based on monostatic sensing setups at relatively low technology readiness levels (TRLs) [3GPP22.837]. In this regard, the 6G-DISAC project responds to this need by advancing the notion of distributed intelligent sensing and communication (DISAC). DISAC broadens the traditional ISAC paradigm by introducing scalable (in terms of the number and heterogeneity of sensing devices, as well as of the overall service coverage), context-adaptive, and semantically aware sensing mechanisms supported by distributed intelligence and network-wide cooperation [CAG+24].

The objective of WP5 within the overall 6G-DISAC framework is to implement and validate the technical concepts developed within work package (WP) 2, WP3 and WP4. In particular, it focuses on the demonstration of ISAC in distributed settings, which includes the associated field measurements in realistic scenarios and relevant frequency bands, validation of novel adaptive waveforms including semantic-aware waveforms, and multi-modal distributed sensing. The underlying network architecture is the one developed within the DISAC framework and detailed in [6GDISAC-D22].

The objective of deliverable D5.2 is to provide a detailed discussion on the selection of components and methods for the demonstrators of the 6G-DISAC framework, thereby addressing work done in both tasks T5.1 and T5.2. This deliverable builds upon previous deliverable [6GDISAC-D51], which defined the key building blocks and interfaces, by selecting and justifying technical methods to be implemented and/or validated in subsequent proof-of-concepts (PoCs) and measurement campaigns (please note that, in this document, we use the terms PoC and Demo interchangeably). In this regard, this deliverable explicitly maps each demonstrator to technical methods from WP3 and WP4, as outlined in [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41], respectively. The selected use cases for demonstration are mapped with the ones defined in WP2 [6GDISAC-D21] and the performance of the implemented technical solutions is evaluated exploiting relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) as outlined in [6GDISAC-D23]. Finally, this deliverable highlights the main architectural elements and their role in the selected demonstrators as detailed in the 6G-DISAC framework [6GDISAC-D22].

1.2 Structure of the Document

The content of this document is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the selected methods and components for the five demonstrators developed within WP5. Here, the methodology of each demonstrator is mapped with methods from WP3 and WP4, as well as with relevant KPIs from WP2. Section 3 provides an overview of the selected hardware (HW) components for the demonstrators, while Section 4 focuses on the implemented software (SW) methods by making explicit connections with the work in WP3 and WP4. Section 5 discusses architectural components in the demonstrators as developed within WP2. Finally, Section 6 provides concluding remarks and discusses next steps within the work of WP5.

2 Demonstration Platforms and Setups

This section provides a detailed description of the 5 demonstrators envisioned to validate the main technical solutions developed within the DISAC framework. In particular, the link between each demonstrator and the technical WPs is highlighted, as well as with the relevant project-level objectives and KPIs.

2.1 Overview of Demonstrator Structure

Table 2-1 below summarizes the planned demonstrators, which are described in detail in the following.

Table 2-1: Overview of planned demos and the respective involved partners.

Demo #	Demo Title	Contributing Partners
#1	DISAC Sounder Based Setup	CEA
#2	DISAC 5G-NR Waveform Testing Platform	NOK
#3	DISAC Semantic Platform	IMS, CEA
#4	DISAC Opportunistic Sensing RIS Platform	NEC
#5	DISAC-assisted parking	BOS, RAD, TIM

Each demonstrator focuses on different key enabling solutions of the 6G-DISAC framework, as developed in the technical WPs. The explicit per-demo mapping is made available in the following, while the broader integration within the technical WPs is discussed in Section 4, and Section 5, for WP3/WP4 and WP2, respectively. The 5 demonstrators are summarized as follows.

- **Demo #1** involves an indoor radio channel measurement campaign emulating distributed ISAC scenarios. The collected data can be used for realistic evaluation of the Project’s technical methods.
- **Demo #2** consists of a testing platform for novel ISAC waveforms, e.g., as developed in WP3, in a real-life monostatic sensing scenario. The collected data can be used for further enhancement of such technical solutions.
- **Demo #3** validates a semantic communication system thorough experimental evaluation, thereby demonstrating the effectiveness of key technical methods, e.g., semantic waveforms, encoding, mapping, and reconstruction.
- **Demo #4** showcases a real-life RIS-aided distributed ISAC setup, in which RISs are deployed to enhance both communication and sensing, leveraging sensing methods derived from the Project’s core outcomes.
- **Demo #5** involved multi-modal distributed sensing and fusion, thereby serving as an umbrella scenario involving and integrating multiple key technical methods from WP2, WP3 and WP4.

2.2 Demo #1: DISAC Sounder Based Setup

2.2.1 Demo Description

This Demo #1, which is conducted by CEA, presents an experimental campaign for radio channel measurements in an indoor environment dedicated to distributed ISAC applications. The

distributed aspect means that detection and communication information is collected and used from multiple spatially separated Base Stations (BSs). In the last years, the so-called upper-mid band or 6G FR3 (7–15 GHz) spectrum, is attracting significant attention. When compared to the 5G FR2 band, it has advantages in terms of path loss and coverage. Meanwhile, compared with 5G FR1, it facilitates the use of a more expansive channel bandwidth. Measurements are performed over a wide bandwidth encompassing both the upper part of frequency range (FR) 1 (i.e., from 400 MHz to 7125 MHz) and the lower part of FR3 (i.e., from 7.125 GHz to 24.25 GHz) [3GPP38.104]. The experimental setup explores three different BS (used as TX) locations and up to seven User Equipment (UE) (used as RX) locations as shown in Figure 2-1 below. The monostatic sensing channels of the BSs and the communication channels with respect to the different UE locations are recorded, while a human phantom (i.e., a standardized human-body surrogate) is moved (along a reproducible path) in the experimental area to simulate body shadowing and backscattering effects. The data thus makes it possible to characterize the behavior of the communication channel in these different spatial configurations and propagation conditions, and not just to identify the presence or position of obstacles. It is used to evaluate the robustness of the link, the variability of the signal, and the overall performance of the transmission system. Covering the needs of communication, sensing, and localisation in a distributed ISAC context, the resulting experimental data is meant to contribute to the experimental validation of several algorithmic approaches developed in WP3 and WP4 (see Sec. 4).

To illustrate more concretely its potential in terms of exploitation, first post-processing results are provided hereafter, where the channel gain is mainly analysed as a function of beam scan angle and body position, profiles, and the power angular-delay profile (PADP). Then, from the extracted multipath components (MPCs) in the angle-delay domain, preliminary detection and localisation results are also shown, relying on basic algorithms and simple heuristics (i.e., besides other studies currently on-going in WP3, which aim at validating advanced and/or more specific algorithms).

The overall scenario for Demo #1 is represented in the figure below, where P1-P10 represent 10 different positions of the human phantom.

Figure 2-1: Overview of the setup for Demo #1.

The positions of the different base stations (BS), the different users (UEs) and the human phantom were represented on the reference coordinate system (x,y) at BS1. Table 2-2 gives the coordinates of these different positions in meters (m).

Table 2-2: Reference point for the positions of base stations, users, and human phantom.

	X (m)	Y (m)		X (m)	Y (m)
UE0	-1,5	4,33	P1	-0,93	2,15
UE1	0	3,8	P2	-0,73	2,15
UE2	0	4,83	P3	-0,53	2,15
UE3	0	5,84	P4	-0,33	2,15
UE4	0	6,83	P5	-0,13	2,15
UE5	0	7,85	P6	0,07	2,15
UE6	0	8,86	P7	0,27	2,15
BS1	0	0	P8	0,47	2,15
BS2	2,25	8,05	P9	0,67	2,15
BS3	-1,85	6,62	P10	0,87	2,15

2.2.2 Demo Objectives

This demonstration aims to provide experimental means for the offline evaluation of KPIs defined by the 6G-DISAC project, with a focus on the characterization of detection and communication performance in a distributed ISAC system, as well as its practical feasibility. The main features and objectives of Demo #1 are summarized below:

- Characterization of the indoor distributed channel: Joint experimental measurement of the communication and detection channels over a wide FR1–FR3 bandwidth to assess the channel's frequency dependence.
- Impact of the human body on propagation: Evaluation of channel gain attenuation and PADP variations due to the presence and blockage of the human body.
- Angular and temporal resolution of PADP: Extraction of power–delay–angle profiles to identify MPCs and characterize their behaviours depending on body position and scanning angle.
- Human detection capability: Reliable identification of human presence based on channel gain drops and PADP profile variations, demonstrating the ISAC system's sensitivity to environmental variations.
- Localisation accuracy: Estimation of user and target positions based on the distributed set of BSs.
- Experimental validation of the DISAC concept: Demonstration of the feasibility of a distributed system simultaneously integrating communication and sensing, in accordance with the DISAC project's KPIs [6GDISAC-D21].

The work presented in this Demo#1 falls directly within the framework of Demo#5, contributing to the validation of the communication, localization and detection performance targeted by this Demo#5. Moreover, as a generic application-agnostic offline validation means, Demo#1 is meant to contribute to the evaluation of most of 6G-DISAC's KPIs [6GDISAC-D21].

2.2.3 Key HW/SW Components and Setup Description

Description of the hardware components used

- 4-port vector network analyzer (VNA): Measures the channel S-parameters and frequency response across a wideband covering FR1 to FR3.
- Two horn antennas: Simulate a BS, with a gain of approximately 20 dBi each.
- Two monopole antennas: Represent the UEs, with a gain of approximately 5 dBi each.
- A phantom: Represents the human body.
- Three antenna positioning systems: Control the rotation of the BSs, the radar target, and the phantom, and create a small-scale spatial grid for the UEs on an (x, y) plane.
- A computer (PC): Controls the various positioners and the vector network analyzer via a MATLAB interface, used for signal generation and measurement of data acquisition.

Description of the measurement setup

A first data acquisition was performed in the frequency domain using a four-port VNA in the 3-11 GHz frequency band, with a frequency step size of 5 MHz. We remark that this measurement campaign could be further extended within the upcoming months, covering the settings announce in [6GDISAC-D51].

The measurement setup included two horn antennas acting as base stations, each with a gain of 13 dBi over a band of 0.45 to 8.45 GHz. The two omnidirectional monopole antennas represented the UE with a gain of approximately 5 dBi. In this study, the beamwidth of the horn antenna directly influences the probability of main lobe blockage, the variability of the received signal, and the sensitivity to propagation effects. The experimental parameters of the measurement system are listed in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3: Measurement system parameters.

Frequency band	[3-11] GHz
Frequency step	5 MHz
Emission power	10 dBm
IF BW	100 Hz

All antennas related to the VNA by calibrated coaxial cables, ensuring measurement accuracy and minimizing insertion losses. The horn antennas were mounted on a motorized positioner allowing controlled angular rotations to explore different azimuth directions. One of the monopole antennas (UE1) was installed on a two-dimensional (x, y) positioner to perform spatial grid measurements (on a 3x3 grid), while the second (UE0) was mounted on a fixed mast. The BS antennas were successively placed at three distinct locations, rotating in angular ranges from -60° to $+60^\circ$ for all UE positions. The phantom was moved between these BS positions to simulate the movement of an indoor pedestrian. The reproducibility of the movement makes it possible to reconstruct complex scenarios in out-of-direct-view situations involving several BS or UE. Regarding the user terminals, UE0 remained fixed, while UE1 was moved to six positions spaced 1 m apart (from UE1 to UE6), forming a grid (3 x 3) at each location to characterize the spatial variability of the propagation channel. A spacing of 1 m between the different reception positions was chosen to ensure sufficient decorrelation of the radio channel between two consecutive measurement points, thus allowing channel-independent realizations to be obtained. Figure 2-2 illustrates the positioning of BS1 and UE1, as well as the movement of the phantom over a distance from 0 to 1800 mm, with a step of 200 mm, corresponding to ten successive positions (P1 to P10).

Figure 2-2: Demo #1 measurement scenario.

The BSs were installed at a height of 1.33 m, corresponding to the height of the user antennas, at the chest level of the phantom representing a human body. The height of the horn antennas at the base stations was chosen so that the human body could block the main lobe of the beam, to study the effect of blocking and detection by the human body. The measurement grid of the user equipment UE1 extends from 0 to 20 mm on the x and y axes, with a step of 10 mm, forming a 3 × 3 measurement grid. The grid dimensions were chosen to be consistent with the wavelength of the signal being studied, to capture significant spatial variations in the electromagnetic field around the EU. The 10 mm grid spacing offers a compromise between the spatial resolution of the measurements and experimental complexity. The 0 to 20 mm extension on the x and y axes allows for the consideration of slight variations in position.

Preliminary post-processing results and illustrations

Channel gain and body shadowing

As a first step, the measured channel transfer function $H_{i,j}(\varphi_s, f)$ is exploited to compute the average channel gain as:

$$CG_{i,j}(\varphi_s) = \frac{1}{BW} \int H_{i,j}(\varphi_s, f) df$$

where φ_s is the considered scanning direction, f is the frequency point index and (i, j) denotes either the monostatic sensing channel ($i = j = BS$) or the one-way communication channel ($i = BS, j = UE$). Figure 2-3 illustrates the obtained results for the UE3 positions and beam steering across the three BS locations.

In Figure 2-3(b), a noticeable power decrease can be observed for the BS--UE link at angles around $\varphi_s = 0$. Conversely, Figure 2-3(a) exhibits a local maximum, corresponding to the backscattering response from BS1. In this configuration, both the body presence and its angular position can be effectively inferred from the power variations observed in the sensing and communication channels. It is also noteworthy that for $\varphi_s > 90^\circ$, the maximum backscattered power at the BS is obtained due to a strong reflection from the metallic door located on the right-hand side. For BS2, the human body position along the x-axis has a negligible impact on both the sensing (BS-BS) and communication (BS-UE) channels, owing to the limited interaction with the dominant propagation paths. A small variation at $\varphi_s = -10^\circ$, in Figure 2-3(c), may still be attributed to body-induced scattering effects.

Figure 2-3: Measured channel gain as a function of the steering angle and body position (along its pre-defined trajectory) for BS-BS and BS-UE channels, and 3 different BS locations.

Finally, for BS3, the body presence influences certain localised angular regions. As shown in Fig. 2-3(e), at $\varphi_s = 60^\circ$ a clear loss in the backscattered response is observed, mainly due to the shadowing of the strong reflector (the metallic door). Similarly, in the BS–UE channel at the same angle, a reduction in channel gain is also present, which can be attributed to the shadowing of secondary multipath components.

Power Angular Delay Profile and Multipath extraction

The measured channel transfer function (CTF) matrix, $h(\varphi_s, f)$, is formed as an $[N_s, N_f]$ matrix, where N_s is the number of scanning directions (steering angles) and N_f is the number of frequency points swept. The steering direction and delay dependent channel impulse response matrix $H(\varphi_s, \tau)$ of dimensions $[N_s, N_\tau]$ is computed following:

$$h(\varphi_s, \tau) = F^{-1}(W(f) \cdot H(\varphi_s, f))$$

where $W(f)$ is the raised cosine window function, $H(\varphi_s, f)$ is the measured channel transfer function, F^{-1} is the inverse Fourier Transform. The PADP matrix, $PADP(\varphi_s, \tau)$, of dimensions $N_s \times N_\tau$ is obtained as follows:

$$PADP(\varphi_s, \tau) = |h(\varphi_s, \tau)|^2$$

The results of the backscattering sensing channel are shown in Figure 2-4 for the different BS locations, and the body positions. Different contributions corresponding to the environment and body backscattering itself are present. Generally, the highest ones correspond to the delay-angular contributions of the highest scatterers, such as walls and metallic doors.

Figure 2-4: PAPD of backscattering channel for position 5 of the body.

The environment scatterers are supposed to poorly change during the measurements, while the main scatterer moving is the human phantom itself. In order to highlight this contribution, the measurement at position 1 of the body, is subtracted to all the other ones for the BS-BS channel, to obtain a clutter reduction. The results are shown in Fig. 2-5(a) for position 2 and Fig. 2-5(c) for position 5. For the BS-UE communication channel, these two positions correspond respectively to a Line-of-Sight (LoS) condition in Fig. 2-5(b) and obstructed LoS in Fig. 2-5(d). The black points have represented the MPCs extracted through a 2D-CLEAN algorithm [CGA+22]. The algorithm iteratively looks for the maximum amplitude α_k in angle φ_k , and associated corresponding delay τ_k , following the hereafter enumerated steps.

- 1) For each body position, build a map by putting together the PDPs associated with all the steering directions.
- 2) Find the maximum value $PM_k = |\alpha_k|^2$ in the PDPs map, and store its value, its delay and angle φ_k ,
- 3) Taking PM_k as a centre point, set to zero all the samples in the rectangular area between $\Delta_\tau = 5ns$ and $\Delta_\varphi = 40^\circ$. This means that PM_k and all the ceil-coloured entries around it are zero. A new cleaned version of the map is obtained, where the local maximum is no more present.
- 4) If at least a value of the new version of the map is above a predefined threshold (e.g., a noise-based one), go to step (2). Otherwise, the algorithm ends when the sum of the recorded MPCs powers reaches a threshold, or when reaching a maximum number of extracted MPCs is obtained.

Figure 2-5: Power Angular Delay Profiles for BS1 for sensing (a)(c) and communication (b)(d).

The results in the angular delay domain are shown in Fig. 2-6(a) for position 2 and Fig. 2-6(b) for position 5. In this illustration the sensing mono-static channel (BS-BS) is illustrated as dot black line, while the communication (BS-UE) channel is illustrated in red line. The example shows how in the position 2 for BS1 the body contribution is relatively reduced because of the incident angle, and the BS-UE LoS path is enhanced. On the contrary on the position 5 the body is obstructing the LoS and clearly identified for angle equal to 0 and range close to 2m. The LoS path of the BS-UE is consequently reduced. It is important to notice that this angular domain representation shows how other secondary MPCs in BS-UE channel are poorly affected by the body position.

Figure 2-6: Extracted MPCs in sensing and communication channels for BS1: LoS (a), obstructed (b).

Examples of application to sensing and localisation

Based on the previous measurement results we analyse here what could be the localisation performance (both the localization of the passive target, i.e., sensing, and the localization of connected UEs) based on a simple time of arrival and angle estimation following the steps described hereafter:

- 1) On the BS-BS channel subtract the environment echo, starting from the first acquisition of the scanning, i.e. $\varphi_s = 60^\circ$;
- 2) Perform a multipath component estimation by means of a CLEAN-2D algorithm, as described in the previous section;
- 3) Select the first two strongest path $[\alpha_1, \varphi_1, T_1]$ and $[\alpha_2, \varphi_2, T_2]$;
- 4) Choose the shortest path $T_m = \min\{T_1, T_2\}$;
- 5) Calculate the range as $d_m = C \cdot \frac{T_m}{2}$ for BS-BS channels and $d_m = C \cdot T_m$ for BS-UE channels.
- 6) Using a geometric approach, we positioned the target and the UE knowing the position of the current base station.

The results of the localisation of the body (i.e., passive object) and UE3 are shown in Fig. 2-7, as observed from different BSs. The actual positions of the BSs and the UE are indicated by dot markers, while the green points represent the body true locations. The localisation of the UE is generally accurate when estimated by BS1 and BS2 with errors between 2 and 30 cm, except in the central positions (5 and 6) of the body, where masking effects strongly impact the MPCs, resulting in misleading position estimates with errors of 5.8m in x. The inaccurate estimation from BS2 mainly arises from the angular discretisation of the beamsteering process and the tilt of BS2 with respect to the x–y axis. A finer beamsteering resolution could easily improve the horizontal (x, y) positioning accuracy of the UE. Overall, the presence of the body is well detected by BS1, with localization errors between 4 and 20 cm on body coordinates. The main errors observed in body localisation from BS2 and BS3 are attributed to the low radar cross section (RCS) caused by the body's orientation with respect to the BS location. For certain positions, BS3 estimates the strongest path as a residual clutter component corresponding to the bottom wall and the metallic door, which would result in a maximum error estimate of 3.7 m for position 8 and 9 of the body. These outliers can be effectively mitigated through cooperative

multi-point sensing and fusion approaches (hence, leveraging a truly distributed ISAC scenario), which will be further investigated in WP3 (See Sec. 4).

Figure 2-7: Sensing and Localization result.

The previous results demonstrate the dependence of the channel gain and the PADP on body position and beam-scanning angle, as well as on the behaviour of the MPCs. It is shown that the presence of the human body can be sensed through noticeable drops in channel gain when the LoS component is obstructed. Partial shadowing of environmental scatterers also produces measurable variations in the monostatic sensing channel. By exploiting distributed multipath information, body presence and user positions can be accurately localised. Although body shadowing may degrade UE localisation accuracy, cooperative sensing among multiple BSs enables centimetre-level precision. Similarly, passive object localisation can be affected by a low radar cross section at specific incidence angles from BSs, but distributed sensing achieves sub-10 cm accuracy in the (x, y) plane.

2.2.4 Methodology

Involved Algorithms from WP3

Beyond the very preliminary exploitation results illustrated above, more generally, the characterised features of both backscattering and communication channels can be leveraged in the context of WP3 for multiple purposes:

- To feed the simulation-based validation and performance assessment of already designed WP3 algorithms, in the same specific deployment scenario as that of Demo#1 (i.e., based on more realistic multipath/backscattering conditions, rather than e.g., considering very generic or overly simplified synthetic models);
- To guide the design of new or refined algorithmic approaches (e.g., with the use of more relevant heuristics based on specific channel behaviour, derivation of optimal forms under realistic operating conditions);
- To calibrate and/or benchmark the simulation tools in use in some specific studies besides (e.g., SIONNA-based deterministic predictions used for the detection of mobile passive targets via machine learning).

Note that the measurement campaigns conducted in the frame of Demo#1 are deliberately multi-purpose and relatively agnostic with respect to the application. Accordingly, as long as a

channel representation is involved at PHY level, the acquired data can hence be relevant to waveform design and PHY layer optimisation in WP3 T3.1, detection and localisation algorithms in T3.2, or even sensing-aided communications in T3.3. The data itself (i.e., raw or pre-processed) can also be made available in various forms and with different levels of abstraction:

- Raw data: complex gains of the overall channel (corresponding to the frequency domain channel transfer function);
- Pre-processed data: Parameters (complex gain, delay, angle-of-arrival (AoA) and/or angle-of-departure (AoD)) of the strongest extracted MPCs.

Finally, thanks to the taken reproducible and multiport VNA-based sounding approach, two important aspects of DISAC testing are covered:

- Synchronization is inherently enabled at system level (i.e., among the multiple acquisition points) so that demanding fully synchronous distributed algorithmic schemes from WP3 can be tested. Asynchronism can also still be emulated offline, by artificially injecting timing offsets over the acquired different links acquired;
- Coherent multi-link channels involving a larger number of devices can be easily re-composed to generate more complex deployment scenarios (offline).

Section 4 summarises possible candidate algorithms from WP3 for offline experimental validations and realistic performance evaluations.

Relevant Protocols from WP4

Demo#1 is not directly related to network protocols. Indeed, since the demonstration is based on channel sounding, besides the scheduling of measurement acquisitions (e.g., depending on metrological requirements and/or emulated offline scenarios), no wireless protocol from WP4 T4.1 has been explicitly implemented or tested. The experimental data is collected according to the established measurement plan, with no event-driven control feedback (i.e., contrary to actual protocols).

However, just like for the offline validation of WP3 algorithms, the acquired channel data can be directly injected in simulation frameworks to evaluate the performance of resource allocation algorithms from T4.2. Moreover, while splitting the overall measurement band into different sub-bands (hence, intrinsically phase-coherent), spectrum management and multi-band algorithms from T4.3 can also be tested offline.

Further precisions about possible WP4 algorithmic candidates can also be found in Section 4.

2.3 Demo #2: DISAC 5G-NR Waveform Testing Platform

2.3.1 Demo Description

As detailed in the previous Deliverable 5.1 section 4.2 [6GDISAC-D51], the Demo#2 is designed for data collection. It uses an existing 5G-New Radio (5G-NR) prototype built by assembling commercial equipment operating in the FR2 frequency band and configured to operate as a monostatic radar (transmitter and receiver in the same location) [Nok-PoC-23]. The system sends an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) waveform and applies a periodogram-based method to derive range and Doppler information about nearby objects. The sensing method is mainly based on pilot signals such as PRS, or any known signal at the receiver side. In this PoC, all the resources are dedicated for sensing, while the communication part is out of the scope of this demo. The scheduling with communication depends on the network load and the service requirements that will be handled by the service provider. The main goal of Demo #2 is to sense and characterise the environment, collecting data on both moving and stationary targets. This real-world data will then be used to build a high-fidelity digital twin of the sensing system, which will support the test of advanced sensing algorithms in WP3 [6GDISAC-D31].

Furthermore, we also expect to leverage the real-world dataset collected from the platform to demonstrate and validate the distributed processing capabilities as proposed in the WP2 architecture. Figure 2-8 illustrates a communication array that has been used for classical communication transmitting known data across the region of interest, while a sniffer array is capturing all reflections from the surrounding environment.

Before any data collection takes place, several prerequisite steps are required, including a calibration phase in which the environment is recorded to compute a clutter correction matrix [CRAP+23] and perform channel correction. The calibrations are mainly related to overcoming all the delays that any connection will introduce in the system and might lead to an error estimation of the delay, i.e. range. This might take several hours depending on the complexity and the size of the region of interest. This process ensures that environmental artifacts and static reflections are mitigated, allowing for more accurate target detection and characterization. These corrections are designed to impose low computational overhead at runtime, enabling efficient operation during real-time sensing.

Figure 2-8: Demo #2 configuration setup with Communication array (TX) and Sniffer (RX) arrays.

2.3.2 Demo Objectives

The objective of this demo is to act as a versatile testing platform that supports the evaluation of multiple project contributions, which can potentially relate to any DISAC KPI. Specifically, the demo aims to validate and refine the algorithms developed within WP3 [6GDISAC-D31], which focus on advanced sensing and signal processing techniques. By testing these algorithms to real measurement data obtained from actual equipment, their effectiveness, performance, and robustness can be evaluated under realistic radio conditions. This validation process is a crucial step toward building a reliable and accurate digital twin of the sensing environment, i.e. a virtual replica that mirrors both the physical and electromagnetic characteristics of real-world scenarios. The digital twin will enable iterative development, optimization, and risk reduction on sensing performance of the algorithms prior to deployment, ensuring system reliability and readiness.

2.3.3 Key HW/SW Components and Setup Description

Figure 2-9 illustrates the hardware equipment utilized for the dataset collection in this setup. The pseudo demo has a monostatic sensing setup with a quasi-co-located gNodeB (gNB) transmit unit and Sniffer receive unit, both operating in the FR2 band at 27.4 GHz with 200 MHz

bandwidth. Configured for time division duplexing (TDD), it allows the receiver to capture reflections of the transmitted OFDM signal for radar-like processing. It should be noted that although the transmitter and receiver are separated by only a few centimetres (Δ distance), the sensed target is located at several meters away. This significant difference in distance justifies the assumption of a monostatic configuration, as the small spatial separation between the transmitting and receiving units has a negligible impact on the sensing geometry and signal processing.

Figure 2-9: Nokia demo equipment for object sensing.

The integrated Signal Processing Unit (SPU) applies advanced OFDM radar algorithms to estimate target range and Doppler via periodogram-based methods.

2.3.4 Methodology

In this pseudo demo, the dataset collection methodology follows a structured process as illustrated in the flowchart shown in Figure 2-10. So, after calibrating the hardware components and synchronizing the transmitter array (TX) and the sniffer array units (RX), the dataset collection is initiated. Thus, the transmitter emits a known reference signal within the FR2 band. The sniffer captures the reflected signals originating from both the surrounding environment and the designated target object. These raw measurement signals are filtered within the SPU to remove noise and enhance data quality. The resulting dataset serves as the foundation for testing and validating the sensing algorithms. For a more comprehensive explanation of the measurement procedure and signal processing chain, readers are referred to [Nok-PoC-23].

Involved Algorithms from WP3

As part of our investigation, the Demo #2 design served as an initial step in shaping the core localisation algorithm. The research described in WP3 and [MEK+25] leverages 5G networks to model localisation algorithms using 5G NR pilot signals, which proposes a new method to enhance passive target localisation in multistatic ISAC systems using 5G NR Positioning Reference Signals (PRS). Traditional localisation approaches such as Least Squares (LS) and Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares (IRLS) often degrade under non-line-of-sight (NLoS) conditions and in the presence of PRS range-resolution errors. To address these challenges, [MEK+25] introduces a technique that mitigates the influence of NLoS paths and PRS resolution

limits by forming difference-of-range measurements across gNBs and UEs. This enables more reliable localisation even without prior knowledge of which links are affected by NLoS.

Figure 2-10: Flowchart of sensing components [Nok-PoC-23].

Relevant Protocols from WP4

As mentioned previously, Demo #2 operates on a real 5G NR network that is fully compliant with 3GPP standards. Consequently, there is no dedicated protocol specifically designed for target localization within this framework. Instead, the RX is preconfigured in a sensing mode, enabling it to collect all echoes present in the surrounding environment. This setup allows the system to exploit existing 5G NR signalling without requiring any modifications to the standardized protocol stack.

2.4 Demo #3: DISAC Semantic Platform

2.4.1 Demo Description

Demo #3 showcases a semantic communication platform aiming to experimentally validate the performance of the new Orthogonal Semantic Sequence Division Multiplexing (OSSDM) waveform designed in WP3 T3.1. It focuses on the integration of semantic encoding with physical-layer waveform generation, establishing a direct bridge between semantic meaning and radio transmission. Demo #3 is a joint software-hardware testbed for algorithmic development, semantic signal design, and physical-layer validation. This waveform is relevant to DISAC since *i)* it allows to efficiently and contextually compress the sensing data collected from distributed sensing nodes to remote fusion centres and/or shared among sensing peers and *ii)* it enables saving PHY resource through multi-purpose sensing/communication waveforms.

The demonstrator implements a complete end-to-end semantic communication chain on a Software-Defined Radio (SDR) hardware (USRP X310). The system processes structured knowledge-graph (KG) inputs, converts them into complex semantic symbols, and maps these onto Walsh-function-based waveforms compliant with 5G/6G spectral masks. It will mimic channel effects such as fading or jamming but will not evaluate real-world scenarios. DISAC contribution will be carried out using input from other demos, and showcase how Demo #3 can be a vector for DISAC using dedicated semantic communications.

Demo #3 is divided into three main parts:

- Semantic encoding and mapping: generation of semantic symbols and mapping to Walsh coefficients through a trained feed-forward neural network constrained by a spectrally compliant codebook.
- Over-the-air transmission: real-time emission and reception of OSSDM waveforms at 2.45 GHz through SDR hardware under controlled noise conditions.
- Semantic reconstruction: recovery of transmitted meaning at the receiver via a semantic decoder, including correlation-based semantic-aware synchronization and semantic feedback equalization.

Figure 2-11: Semantic communication chain with USRP operations.

Figure 2-12: Demo#3 testbed with USRP, computer control and cables.

2.4.2 Demo Objectives

Demo#3 targets the semantic communication efficiency objectives defined in [6GDISAC-D21] and [6GDISAC-D23] contributing to the following KPIs:

- Semantic accuracy: ability to preserve the intended meaning across the transmission chain, measured via F1-score between transmitted and reconstructed knowledge graphs.
- Spectral efficiency: optimisation of semantic information conveyed per occupied Hz, leveraging spectrally efficient OSSDM-coded waveforms.
- Energy efficiency: reduction of transmitted data volume by encoding semantic content with OSSDM rather than raw bits.
- Communication reliability: semantic-aware synchronisation and equalisation ensure robust recovery even under severe noise or hardware impairments. The demo will only use standard channel evaluation, such as artificial fading, and will not include any real-world mobility scenario due to test bench limitations.

2.4.3 Key HW/SW Components and Setup Description

Hardware Setup

- SDR platform: 2 × USRP X310 units (TX/RX) with 200 MHz bandwidth.
- Carrier frequency: 2.45 GHz (ISM band).
- Antenna configuration: 2 omnidirectional 2.4 GHz antennas for transmission and reception.
- Host computers: Python/MATLAB interface for real-time signal generation, control, and analysis.
- Spectrum Analyzer: for emission mask and spectral compliance validation.

Software Chain

- Semantic encoder: graph neural network (GNN) extracting node embeddings from knowledge graphs. No complexity will be evaluated in this demo.
- Symbol mapper: feed-forward network (FFN) mapping embeddings to complex semantic symbols.
- Walsh mapper and codebook generator: neural mapping to Walsh coefficients constrained by a pre-generated spectrally compliant codebook (approx. 10000 codewords).
- Waveform generator: Inverse Walsh Transform (IWT) to produce time-domain signals.

Measurement Setup: experiments are conducted under two scenarios:

- SDR noise only: characterisation of hardware-induced imperfections (quantization, phase noise).
- SDR noise + additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN): addition of controlled channel noise to evaluate semantic robustness from -10 dB to $+10$ dB signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

2.4.4 Methodology

Involved Algorithms from WP3

The methodology builds on several key algorithms developed within WP3. The Orthogonal Semantic-Symbol Division Multiplexing (OSSDM) scheme introduces a joint semantic–physical layer waveform architecture based on Walsh functions, enabling efficient multiplexing of semantic symbols at the waveform level. In addition, a Correlation-based Semantic-Aware Synchronization (CSAS) mechanism is employed to align transmitted and received signals by maximizing semantic fidelity, measured through metrics such as the F1-score, rather than relying solely on

conventional cross-correlation peaks. This approach significantly reduces semantic information loss under channel impairments. Furthermore, semantic feedback equalization is incorporated as a closed-loop technique, whereby decoded semantic representations are re-projected onto the physical layer to correct symbol warping and mitigate accumulated distortions during transmission.

Relevant Protocols from WP4

The proposed methodology is supported by communication protocols defined in WP4, which ensure interoperability and efficient coordination within the DISAC architecture. The Semantic Exchange Protocol standardizes the structure of semantic symbols and governs the exchange of semantic object metadata between network nodes, enabling consistent interpretation across the system. Complementarily, the Resource Orchestration for Semantic Waveforms protocol manages semantic-aware transmission scheduling and feedback mechanisms, dynamically allocating resources in accordance with semantic priorities and channel conditions to optimize end-to-end performance.

2.5 Demo #4: DISAC Opportunistic Sensing RIS Platform

2.5.1 Demo Description

Demo#4 is planned to be a distributed *opportunistic* RIS-aided sensing use case, whereby sensing information (i.e., user localization) is extracted from the communication operations without any disruption. As depicted in Figure 2-13, we consider a scenario wherein two RISs are deployed to serve a UE for communication purposes. Moreover, each RIS is connected to its own controller, which is equipped with a machine learning (ML) agent dubbed as *COLoRIS*. The latter infers the position of the user based on the communication parameters of both RISs, without interfering with their communication operations. Both estimated positions are then fused together to improve accuracy.

Figure 2-13: Distributed RIS-based opportunistic sensing use case.

2.5.2 Demo Objectives

We exploit the following relevant sensing-oriented KPIs, as detailed in [6GDISAC-D21] and [6GDISAC-D23] of this project.

- **Sensing accuracy:** difference between the sensed and real values in range, angle, orientation and velocity
- **Sensing resolution:** separation between multiple objects in range, angle, and velocity
- **Sensing range/coverage area:** maximum distance over which the proposed sensing system can detect and interpret signals.
- **Sensing latency:** the time difference between the trigger of the sensing process and the outcome
- **Energy efficiency:** the amount of sensing service delivered per unit of energy consumed (thanks to the use of passive RISs)

2.5.3 Key HW/SW Components and Setup Description

The main HW component in this demonstrator is represented by the RISs. In this regard, we employ two NEC RIS 2025 devices, each one consisting of two boards: the reflection board and the control board, as shown in Fig. 2-14. The reflection board consists of 256 patch antennas in a 16×16 grid of unit cells (each with one antenna), implemented with printed circuit board (PCB) technology on a board with a thickness of around 2 mm. The antennas are separated by a distance equal to $\lambda/2$, both horizontally and vertically, with λ being the wavelength of the supported carrier signals. The operating frequency of the RIS is 5 GHz and thanks to 3-bits delay lines-based phase shifter, 7 different phase shifts equally spaced between 0° and 360° can be chosen for every unit cell, which has been shown to provide precise beamforming capabilities [RMG+24]. The 8th state is dedicated to the absorption mode, which redirects the incoming signal through a 50Ω resistor that dissipates the incoming signal. The RIS is designed to be a modular device. This means that multiple RIS boards can be connected together, thus creating a larger RIS, while still respecting the $\lambda/2$ inter-element distance even between cross-board elements.

Figure 2-14: NEC RIS 2025 prototype: reflection board (left) and control board (right).

The controller can be plugged into the back of the reflection board and mounts the Micro Controller Unit (MCU) to command the RIS. COLoRIS will run on the MCU alongside the usual RIS control operations.

In addition to the RISs (including both reflection and control boards), we exploit the following HW:

- 3 SDR devices to generate the signals and process the received signals.
- 2 horn antennas to illuminate the RIS boards.
- 1 dipole/horn antenna for the UE to receive the signal
- 1 PC to coordinate the control of the 2 NEC RISs

The measurement setup is designed to demonstrate opportunistic localization in an indoor/outdoor environment using two RISs. A base station equipped with multiple antennas transmits downlink signals that reach the UE directly as well as through reflections from RIS₁ and RIS₂, which are deployed at different positions to provide spatial diversity. The two RIS are already set with the best configuration maximising the received power at the UE side (e.g., by applying the method in [EDR+25] in a time-sequential manner). The UE collects the resulting composite signal and reports measurements such as received signal strength or channel indicators. In parallel, each RIS controller shares the applied configurations with a dedicated COLoRIS engine, which processes both the configuration data and the UE measurements to infer a position estimate (details available in [EDR+25] and [6GDISAC-D31]). In this regard, we explore different levels of cooperation and information sharing, ranging from a central fusion of the single UE measurement reports and RIS configurations into a single COLoRIS engine, to weighted fusion of the estimated UE locations processed locally at each distributed implementation of COLoRIS. We assume that during the timeframe necessary for the execution of this method the UE remains stationary. However, mobility of the UE is allowed as long as it happens on a larger time scale, i.e., slower than the execution of the sensing algorithm.

This setup enables high-accuracy positioning without requiring RIS reconfiguration for localisation, as the method exploits communication-driven configurations while benefiting from the diversity provided by the two RIS panels. Note that the performance of the deployed system relies on the environmental conditions, i.e., clutter, multipath, etc., which may partially mask the signal contribution from the direct *virtual* LoS link between the TX, the RIS, and the UE, and on the employed hardware, i.e., the gain and beamwidth of the horn antennas used to illuminate the RISs, the discrete phase-shifts at each unit cell of the RIS, etc. While the hardware limitations are dictated by the available resources, the employed method in [EDR+25] is designed to account for realistic discrete RIS hardware. Moreover, the effect of multipath propagation can be mitigated by collecting samples of the received signal without the RIS and subtracting them from the measurements (see [BSE+25] for details).

2.5.4 Methodology

Involved Algorithms from WP3

The localisation method is an extension of the work described in [6GDISAC-D31] and in [EDR+25] to the case of multiple distributed RISs. In particular, the baseline method is given by contribution #B-7. However, in line with the DISAC framework, in this demonstrator such method is extended to the case of distributed RISs, which are both used to serve a UE under a common BS in a time-separated manner. Each RIS controller runs a local version of the COLoRIS agent, thereby acting as a local sensing processing function (LSePF) (see [6GDISAC-D22]). Each LSePF obtains an estimate of the UE location exploiting the COLoRIS agent, which requires only the current RIS configuration used in the communication process as input. The resulting

information is sent to a central sensing processing function (CSePF) for data fusion by averaging the two results.

Relevant Protocols from WP4

Since multiple distributed RISs need to be coordinated, the relevant network protocols adopted in this demo are described in [6GDISAC-D41], contribution #P-3. In particular, this contribution outlines the message exchange between the distributed RISs, its associated controllers acting as LSePF, and the BS, acting as CSePF, as well as with the UE.

Moreover, as discussed in contribution #O-4, the information on the UE position obtained after signal fusion is then forwarded to the network, which exploits it to refine resource allocation and orchestration methods, such as the BS and/or RIS beamforming configuration. The demonstrated setup involves running two instances of the COLoRIS algorithm locally at each RIS controller and sending the final output to the central CSePF, thereby requiring a degree of computing power at the RIS controller, and minimal signalling overhead. On the other hand, sending directly the raw data to the CSePF before processing at the RIS controller may reduce the computational (and consequently power) requirement at each RIS controller at the cost of increased signalling. Hybrid methods may provide an optimised balance between the allocation of such resources.

2.6 Demo #5: DISAC-Assisted Parking

2.6.1 Demo Description

The objective of this demonstrator is to showcase how a sensor-rich infrastructure, comprising radar, light detection and ranging (LiDAR), camera sensors, RIS, and a fusion server/mobile edge computing (MEC) layer, can extend vehicle perception beyond onboard sensors. The system enables:

- a. identification and authentication of the vehicle (user) upon entering the parking facility,
- b. detection and classification of suitable parking slots for the approaching vehicle, and
- c. provision of navigation assistance and safety warnings to the driver or the vehicle's control unit.

At higher levels of automation, the same infrastructure can further support semi- or fully automated parking manoeuvres by transmitting motion commands and safety-critical information to the vehicle. This demonstrator acts as an umbrella scenario, integrating some of the key results and technical components from WP2, WP3 and WP4, as well as from other demonstrators, into a single proof of concept for infrastructure-assisted perception and navigation.

In this demo, we identify three peripheral ingredients, which are essential to future DISAC wireless systems: *i*) coping with spatially distributed sensors (i.e., in addition to accommodating heterogeneous modalities, as well as various qualities of sensing information), *ii*) the need to orchestrate the sensing/communication tasks in such complex operating contexts (exploiting dedicated architecture blocks), and *iii*) the need to represent the sensing data in relevant formats (e.g., prone to cooperative fusion).

Beyond these elements, Demo #5 concretely demonstrates the DISAC concept by tightly integrating joint sensing and communication functions into a unified system that supports a real, safety-critical application. The demonstrator shows how infrastructure-based sensing, cooperative perception, and low-latency communication combine to deliver actionable information to a vehicle, thereby exemplifying the DISAC vision of a network that simultaneously provides communication services and high-resolution situational awareness. The mixed indoor–outdoor na-

ture of the scenario, the need for reliable perception in GNSS-denied conditions, and the orchestration of multi-modal sensing with real-time data exchange make this demo a tangible and system-level illustration of DISAC principles in practice.

Figure 2-15: Overview of the setup for demo #5 (Assisted Parking) at the Bosch site in Hildesheim (Germany). Blue rectangles indicate the positions of the cameras, red rectangles correspond to LiDAR sensors, green squares denote the potential RIS elements, and the yellow squares (hard line) represent the planned location of Radchat radar units.

Figure 2-16: The demo setup from another perspective.

Demo #5 Step-by-Step Run

Below is a concise runbook for the Assisted Parking demo (a.k.a. Demo #5). It describes the sequence of actions, the messages exchanged, processing steps, and what to show/measure at each stage.

Overview

The demonstrator is executed in two phases:

- **Phase 1 – Identification & authentication:** detect vehicle presence and bind an authenticated vehicle session to the infrastructure.
- **Phase 2 – Sensing, fusion and guidance:** activate sensing, fuse multi-sensor data into ISO 23150 object lists [ISO+23], compute parking-slot suitability and navigation outputs, deliver collective perception message (CPM)-like messages to the vehicle, and (optionally) enable automated parking control.

Step-by-Step Run

In this subsection, we detail the different steps for Demo #5.

Step 1 – Vehicle at initial state, identification and authentication: The vehicle (user) is inside the building shown in Figure 2-15. The short-range radars (which are part of Radchat system) detect its presence and identify the vehicle based on its ultrasonic unique signature. This allows the infrastructure to authenticate the user (vehicle).

The ultrasonic waveform with multiple phase modulated tones is prestored on authorised vehicles. Playing the waveform with onboard audio systems results in window vibrations that can be detected by the short-range radar. The waveforms are designed to be outside the audible range for regular people to minimize the disturbance for the driver and-or passengers.

The waveform contains several phase-modulated sub-frequencies, i.e., (31 Hz, 52 Hz and 68 Hz), which provides 3 bits for each symbol.

The radar is operated on the target object detection mode, where different targets in the field of view (FoV) will be detected and separated with classical sparse Fourier approximation reconstruction (SFAR) algorithms and the list of detected targets is transferred by USB-serial port to a compact edge computer node. The sampling rate for target list update is 26 Hz, which is below the modulated ultrasonic waveform. An equivalent sampling technique is used for demodulation and data extraction. Several repeated waveforms are captured in order to obtain modulated vehicle ID code in the edge computer node. Once the ID code is captured, the target location and ID will be stored and processed for further scenario operations, i.e., open the gate or trigger alarm.

Step 2 – Triggering of phase 2 (sensing orchestration): Once the vehicle has been successfully identified and authenticated, the centralised sensing processing function (CSePF) initiates the orchestration phase by signalling the orchestration and resource manager to activate the relevant sensing components. The activated set of sensors and RIS elements could then be selected dynamically based on the vehicle's position, trajectory, and surrounding context within the parking facility.

Eventually, the orchestrator could compute a short-term sensing plan that optimizes coverage and efficiency for the identified vehicle. This plan includes, for example:

- the sampling rates for LiDAR and camera sensors, and
- the beam configurations and timing sequences for the RIS to enhance coverage in occluded or low-visibility regions.

Note that in this context, *efficiency* refers to several complementary aspects of the orchestration process. First, it concerns the selective activation of sensing modalities depending on the vehicle's position and dynamics, ensuring that only the sensors providing relevant information at a given moment are triggered, thereby avoiding unnecessary processing and data transmission. Second, efficiency relates to tailoring the type and granularity of sensing data to the requirements of the situation, for example adjusting update rates or measurement density when the vehicle is approaching complex areas. Finally, in more intricate parking layouts, efficiency also

encompasses supporting the vehicle in following the most suitable trajectory, both in terms of obstacle avoidance and optimal pacing—by ensuring that sensing resources are allocated in a manner that best enables safe and timely manoeuvring toward the selected parking slot.

Step 3 – Data acquisition and local pre-processing: Following orchestration, each active sensor enters its operational mode and begins acquiring raw measurements of the surrounding environment. Every sensor node, or LSePF, performs local pre-processing, such as object detection, clustering, and classification, before transmitting its outputs to the CSePF.

Each LSePF generates an ISO 23150-compliant object list, including object identifiers, spatial coordinates, velocities, dimensions, class labels, confidence levels, and timestamps. This local processing reduces the upstream data volume and provides a standardized, interoperable representation of the sensed environment.

Step 4 – Multi-sensor fusion and environment modelling: At the next stage, the CSePF aggregates the ISO 23150 object lists from all connected sensors. It performs time alignment, data association, and multi-sensor fusion to maintain a unified and dynamically updated model of the environment. The result is a consistent, high-precision environmental model that forms the basis for parking-slot detection and navigation decisions. This model is continuously updated in real time as new sensor data arrive.

Step 5 – Parking slot detection and suitability evaluation: Based on the fused perception map, the CSePF executes a parking-slot detection and suitability evaluation algorithm. Free-space geometry and static markings are analysed to detect available parking slots. Each candidate slot is then evaluated against the authenticated vehicle's characteristics, such as its dimensions, turning radius, and entry angle, to compute a parking suitability score. The CSePF ranks the available slots and compiles a list containing the slot identifiers, geometric parameters, suitability scores, and recommended approach vectors. This information is prepared for dissemination to the vehicle as part of the CPM-like message payload.

Step 6 – Occlusion management and RIS reconfiguration: When the fused map reveals occluded or low-visibility zones that may conceal obstacles or vulnerable road users, the CSePF dynamically reconfigures the RIS elements to illuminate those regions. By adjusting the phase profiles and beam directions of the RIS panels, the system enhances radar and communication coverage without requiring additional transmitters. This closed-loop adaptation between the CSePF and RIS controller ensures that critical areas of the parking environment remain observable even under challenging geometries or multipath conditions.

Step 7 – Message generation and transmission to the vehicle: Finally, the CSePF compiles the fused perception data and parking recommendations into a CPM-like message destined for the vehicle. This message is expected to contain:

- a filtered object list with the most relevant dynamic and static objects,
- the ranked list of available parking slots,
- the corresponding parking suitability scores, and
- a recommended approach or trajectory.

The message is transmitted to the vehicle interface (UE) via a 3GPP-compliant or vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication link. While the demonstrator relies on existing standards to ensure interoperability and ease of integration, future DISAC deployments could incorporate more specialized transmission schemes in line with the 6G communication standards. In particular, advanced waveforms and protocol enhancements currently investigated in WP3 and WP4 may offer improved joint sensing-communication performance. Depending on the vehicle's Society of Automotive Engineers (known as SAE) automation level, the information is either visualized to assist the human driver or consumed by the vehicle's control unit for semi- or fully automated parking manoeuvres.

2.6.2 Demo Objectives

Demo #5 aims to validate the DISAC concept in the context of assisted parking by integrating multi-modal infrastructure sensing, cooperative perception, and standardized vehicle interfaces. In alignment with the KPI-demo mapping defined in [6GDISAC-D23], this demo directly addresses the following KPIs: communication performance, user/target localisation accuracy and target detection capability.

Specifically, the objectives of Demo #5 are to:

- Assess user/target localisation accuracy in mixed indoor–outdoor parking scenarios, by combining infrastructure-mounted sensors (radar, LiDAR, camera), vehicle data, and transitions between GNSS-denied and GNSS-available areas. This directly contributes to the **localisation accuracy KPI**, evaluating how DISAC-supported sensing improves position, orientation, and trajectory estimation needed for safe parking manoeuvres. Evaluate target detection capability, focusing on the reliable detection of static obstacles, parking-slot features, and VRUs. The demonstrator tests how multi-modal perception and cooperative sensing increase robustness against occlusions and difficult indoor environments, supporting the **target detection capability KPI**.
- Validate communication performance for the exchange of perception information and guidance messages toward the vehicle. The use of a 3GPP-compliant or V2X communication link enables the evaluation of **reliability, latency, and timely data delivery**, in line with the **communication performance KPI**. The demo also provides a basis for future enhancements using DISAC-optimized waveforms and protocols (WP3/WP4).

Through these objectives, Demo #5 acts as the integrated system-level validation point for cooperative sensing and communication in an assisted-parking use case. The scenario provides measurable, realistic data that contribute directly to the DISAC project's final KPI evaluation for communication reliability, localisation accuracy, and detection performance.

Main Functional Blocks

The overall system architecture of the Assisted Parking demonstrator consists of the following main functional building blocks.

Centralised Sensing Processing Function (CSePF) / Fusion Server

The CSePF serves as the central processing unit of the system. It receives ISO 23150-compliant object lists from all connected sensors and could perform the following operations:

- Data association,
- Multi-sensor fusion,
- Parking slot detection and suitability scoring, and
- Generation of navigation and warning messages toward the vehicle.

The CSePF will be hosted on an edge server, ensuring low-latency processing and reliable operation in indoor environments. Its operational logic will be optimized according to technical methods from WP2, WP3 and WP4 (more details in future deliverables).

Security and Identification Module

This module manages the vehicle identification and authentication process at the entry of the parking facility.

General data protection regulation (GDPR) constraints in Europe limit camera-based vehicle authentication. This project implements an identification module that detects ultrasound waveforms using a 120 GHz Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM)-band radar. The system has two parts: on the vehicle side, a predefined multitone ultrasound signature (inaudible) is played

when authorisation is required; on the infrastructure side, a 120 GHz ISM radar detects approaching vehicles and other objects, and measures signature-induced vibrations to confirm whether the vehicle is authorised to park at the location. The identification module comprises the radar and a compact box PC that interfaces with the former, performs signal processing to generate a target list, and verifies the target ID from the detected signature.

Successful authentication triggers at the CSePF level the activation of the relevant sensing and fusion processes for the specific vehicle session.

Sensor Layer

The infrastructure layer consists of multiple sensor modalities that collaboratively capture the surrounding environment:

- **RADCHAT radars:** Using ISM band 120 GHz radar for detection, this band requires no operation license yet has a coverage of 5-10 meter. High carrier frequency of this radar provides vibration detection capability of several micrometers.
- **LiDAR and cameras:** Provide high-resolution geometric and semantic information for object classification and parking slot recognition.
- **RIS elements:** Extend sensing or communication coverage in non-line-of-sight or occluded areas; configurable dynamically through a **RIS Controller** interface:
 - a commercial RIS operating at 26-30 GHz with angles of incidence/reflection in the range of ± 60 deg and an HPBW of 4-6 deg.
 - a frequency up/down converter, which covers most 5G-NR FR2 bands as well as lower broadbands (RF: 24-44 GHz; IF: 0.01-14 GHz)

Each sensor node or LSePF outputs ISO 23150-compliant object lists containing object identifiers, positions, velocities, dimensions, classes, and confidence levels, thereby reducing network load and ensuring interoperability among heterogeneous sensing technologies. More details on the sensors are provided in section 2.6.3.

Vehicle Interface (UE Side)

The vehicle receives CPM-like messages from the EFC containing fused object lists and parking slot recommendations. Depending on the SAE automation level, the information is either:

- displayed to the driver via an in-vehicle visualization interface (SAE Level 2), or
- used by the vehicle control unit to execute automated parking manoeuvres (up to SAE Level 4).

2.6.3 Key HW/SW Components and Setup Description

The DISAC-Assisted Parking demonstrator integrates a diverse set of hardware and software components to achieve its goal of extending vehicle perception through a sensor-rich infrastructure. This section details the key hardware components, with a particular focus on the sensor layer, which is fundamental to the demonstrator's environmental sensing capabilities.

The sensor layer is designed as a multi-modal system, combining the strengths of different sensing technologies to create a comprehensive and robust perception of the parking environment. This approach ensures redundancy and enhances performance in challenging conditions, such as occlusions, poor lighting, or adverse weather. The primary sensors deployed in this demonstrator are LiDARs, cameras, and various types of radars, complemented by RIS to extend sensing coverage.

Below is a detailed description of each sensor component used in the test setup.

LiDARs

The primary LiDAR sensor used is the Hesai QT128C2X [Hes-25]. This is a high-resolution, automotive-grade LiDAR sensor designed for near-range and blind-spot detection, making it well-suited for the intricacies of a parking environment.

Figure 2-17: The Hesai QT128C2X LiDAR.

The QT128C2X features 128 laser channels, providing a dense point cloud that enables precise object detection, classification, and localization. Its high resolution is crucial for identifying the geometry of parking slots, detecting small obstacles, and accurately mapping the static environment. In the context of Demo #5, the LiDAR provides the foundational high-resolution geometric data for the fusion system.

Cameras

Visual information is provided by the DINION IP Starlight 7000HD camera. This is an advanced surveillance camera known for its excellent performance in low-light conditions.

Figure 2-18: Illustration of Bosch's DINION IP starlight 7000 HD.

This camera provides high-definition video streams that are essential for semantic understanding of the scene. Unlike LiDAR or radar, cameras excel at recognizing visual cues such as parking space markings, traffic signs, and distinguishing between different types of objects (e.g., pedestrians, vehicles, shopping carts). The "Starlight" technology ensures reliable performance even in poorly lit indoor parking facilities, which is a key operational requirement for this demonstrator.

Radars

Bosch Gen5 Front Radar

The setup incorporates a **Bosch front radar, Gen 5**. This is a mature and widely used automotive radar that provides robust detection and tracking of objects.

The Gen 5 radar is a staple of advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS). It operates in the 77 GHz band and is primarily used for forward-collision warning and adaptive cruise control. Within this demonstrator, it contributes to detecting the presence and motion of vehicles and other objects, offering reliable velocity and range measurements that are less affected by weather or lighting conditions compared to cameras or LiDARs.

RADCHAT Radars

Besides the overall system architecture and orchestration, one more key innovation in this demonstrator is the use of **RADCHAT radars** for vehicle identification and fine-grained sensing.

As described above, these sensors operate in the 120 GHz ISM band. This frequency band offers two significant advantages: it does not require an operational license, simplifying deployment; and its high carrier frequency enables the detection of micro-vibrations (on the order of several micrometres). This unique capability is exploited for vehicle identification, as described in Section 2.5.3. Furthermore, with a coverage of 5-10 meters, these radars are perfectly suited for near-range applications like detecting a vehicle's arrival at the entrance of a parking facility.

RIS Elements

To address challenges related to NLoS and occluded areas, the demonstrator will incorporate RIS elements. These surfaces are designed to intelligently control and redirect radio waves, effectively extending the coverage of other sensors, particularly radar.

The planned RIS elements include:

- **A commercial RIS panel** operating at 26-30 GHz. It features a wide range of incidence/reflection angles (± 60 degrees) and a narrow Half Power Beamwidth (HPBW) of 4-6 degrees, allowing for precise control of reflected signals.
- **A frequency up/down converter** to bridge different frequency bands, covering RF signals in the range 24-44 GHz and IF signals in the range 0.01-14 GHz. This allows the RIS to be integrated with existing SDR-based communication systems operating at sub-6GHz.

We remark that such devices are not the same as the ones used in Demo #4.

In the parking scenario, an RIS can be dynamically configured via its controller to "illuminate" areas hidden from direct view of the primary radar sensors, such as behind pillars or other parked vehicles, thereby enhancing safety and situational awareness.

2.6.4 Methodology

Involved Algorithms from WP3

In addition to demonstrating the end-to-end workflow of assisted parking, this setup provides a flexible experimental platform for integrating and evaluating several algorithms developed within WP3. In particular, the demonstrator enables the deployment and benchmarking of multi-modal fusion methods that combine LiDAR, camera, RADCHAT radar, frequency-modulated continuous wave (FMCW) radar, and RIS-assisted measurements into a unified perception model. A detailed technical description of this fusion scheme will be provided in future WP3 deliverables.

Beyond this fusion and sensing-orchestration layer, Demo #5 is designed to act as an open test platform for additional WP3 contributions. In particular, the presence of RIS elements allows for testing RIS-aware sensing and control algorithms, including adaptive beam shaping, occlusion mitigation strategies, and environment-aware reconfiguration policies. Overall, Demo #5 serves

as a practical validation environment where WP3 techniques can be assessed under realistic indoor parking conditions and measured against WP5 KPIs.

Relevant Protocols from WP4

This demonstrator tightly relates to the main technological elements from WP4. Indeed, the involved multi-modal sensing is associated with supporting network protocols, such as the ones developed in T4.1 and described in [6GDISAC-D41]. Specifically, the protocols designed to support communication between heterogeneous devices, which may be acting as LSePF, the CSePF, and the special case of RISs whose configuration is controlled by the network. Moreover, the underlying orchestration of the available resources in terms of both communication and sensing of such heterogeneous and distributed nodes interacting together may be optimized according to the contributions made in T4.2.

3 Selected Hardware Components

The diverse DISAC functionalities explored in WP3, which span physical-layer optimisation, adaptive waveform design, cooperative sensing, localisation, and sensing-aided communications, lead to a wide range of hardware requirements for the demonstrator platforms. This section summarises these requirements by mapping each selected contribution to its needed device types, antenna configurations, operating frequencies, bandwidths, synchronisation levels, and assumptions on passive or dynamic objects. The resulting overview provides a concise foundation for selecting and integrating the appropriate HW components under WP5, ensuring scalable and representative validation of the DISAC framework across varied real-world scenarios.

3.1 Overview of HW Requirements

Based on the research works from WP3, several demonstrable contributions are selected as shown in Table 3-1. The rows of the table are grouped by three colours such that they correspond to the three major categories of WP3 contributions: (A) physical-layer optimisation and adaptive waveform design; (B) sensing, localisation, and tracking of active and passive objects; and (C) sensing-aided communications. Across these three groups of contributions, the main hardware requirements include the types of devices involved (e.g., TX/RX nodes, multi-antenna BSs, UEs, RIS panels, and full-duplex ISAC nodes), antenna configurations (single-antenna, multi-antenna, or dynamic metasurface antenna (DMA)-based arrays), supported frequency bands (ranging from 2.4 GHz up to 120 GHz), and the necessary operating bandwidths (from kHz-level narrowband to several-hundred-MHz wideband operation). Additional requirements include synchronization capabilities—ranging from no synchronization to coarse or tight timing/clock alignment—and the characteristics of passive objects (static, mobile, or reflective). More detailed hardware specifications and implementation guidelines can be found in 6G-DISAC Deliverable D3.1 [6GDISAC-D31].

Table 3-1: Overview of the system setups for each demonstrable contribution (WP3) and the associated relevant demo.

Contribution	Required physical devices (UE, BS, RIS, TX, RX, etc.) and how many	Antennas at each device	Uplink or downlink	Preferred frequency band	Preferred bandwidth	Synchronization requirements (time, frequency, phase) and between which devices	Passive object information (static, dynamic, number)	Relevant DEMO
A-1	1 sensing transmitter (TX node), 1 receiver node (RX)	TX: Single antenna, RX: Single antenna	UL	2.4 GHz	10 MHz	None	None	3
A-2	1 TX node (BS), 1 or more RX nodes (UEs), 1 or more RIS	TX: Single antenna (BS), RX: Single antenna (UEs), RIS: Multi-antenna	DL	28 GHz	Up to 400 MHz	Coarse time synchronization (treated as unknown, UE and BS by default)	Stationary, number not determined	4

A-3	1 TX node (BS), 1 RX node (UE), 1 RIS	TX: Multi-antenna (BS), RX: Single antenna (UE), RIS: Multi-antenna	UL/DL	28 GHz	Up to 400 MHz	Coarse time synchronization	Stationary, number not determined	1
A-4	1 monostatic ISAC node (integrated TX/RX), 1 communication RX node	ISAC node: Multi-antenna, RX node: Multi-antenna	DL	28 GHz	Up to 400 MHz	None (monostatic system with shared clock between integrated TX and RX)	Mobile, number not determined	2
A-5	1 dual-functional MIMO BS (integrated TX/RX), multiple single-antenna UEs	BS: Multi-antenna, UEs: Single antenna, targets: Single antenna	DL	Agnostic	Agnostic	None	Stationary, multiple targets/eavesdroppers	2
B-1	1 BS, 1 RIS, 1 UE	BS: Multi-antenna, UE: Multi-antenna, RIS: Multi-element	DL	28 GHz	1 GHz	None	None	4
B-2	1 BS, multiple RISs, 1 UE	BS: Single antenna, UE: Single antenna, RIS: Multi-element	DL	28 GHz	100 kHz	None	None	4
B-5	1 TX, 1 RX	TX: Single antenna, RX: Multi-antenna dynamic metasurface antenna (DMA)	UL	28 GHz	150 kHz	None	None	2
B-6	3 Beacons, 1 Mobile RIS, 1 UE	Beacons: Single antenna, UE: Single antenna, RIS: Multi-element	UL/DL	Agnostic	Narrowband	Time synchronization required	None	4
B-7	1 BS, 1 RIS, 1 UE	BS: Multi-antenna, RIS: Multi-element, UE: Single antenna	UL/DL	Agnostic	Narrowband	Time synchronization required	None	4
B-11	Multiple single-antenna UEs (TX), multiple multi-antenna BSs (RX)	TX: Single antenna, RX: Multi-antenna	UL	28 GHz	400 MHz	Time synchronization among BSs	Stationary scattering/reflecting objects	5
B-13	1 MIMO BS, 1 RIS, 1 UE	BS: Multi-antenna, RIS: Multi-element, UE: Single antenna	DL	28 GHz	10 MHz	None	Drone, mobile	4
B-14	1 single-antenna TX, multiple single-antenna RX nodes	TX: Single antenna, RX: Single antenna	DL	Agnostic	Agnostic	Time synchronization among RX nodes (not TX)	Multiple static solid objects	1
C-2	1 full-duplex MIMO node, multiple UEs, multiple targets	FD node: Multi-antenna DMA (TX/RX), UEs: Multi-antenna	Full-duplex	28 GHz	150 kHz	None	None	2
C-3	1 BS, 1 UE	BS: Multi-antenna DMA, UE: Single antenna	UL	28 GHz	Narrowband	None	None	2

3.2 Transceivers and Antenna Configurations

The selected WP3 contributions require a broad range of transceiver architectures, reflecting the diversity of DISAC functionalities. Several demonstrations employ single-antenna transmitters and receivers (e.g., A-1, B-5), enabling lightweight sensing or communication tasks at lower frequencies. More complex setups (e.g., A-3, A-4, B-1, B-13, C-2) rely on multi-antenna BSs, multi-antenna UEs, or integrated TX/RX ISAC nodes, which support beamforming, spatial filtering, and multi-target processing. Some configurations further incorporate full-duplex transceivers or DMA-based arrays (e.g., B-5), highlighting the need for radios capable of simultaneous transmission and reception and adaptable radiation patterns. These heterogeneous transceiver options form the backbone of the WP3 demonstrations, enabling both high-resolution sensing and efficient communication in diverse deployments.

3.3 RIS

RIS modules appear in a significant portion of the WP3 demonstrations, particularly in the B-series scenarios and the higher-frequency A-2 and A-3 setups. The required RIS hardware ranges from simple reflective panels to multi-element programmable surfaces used for beam steering or environment shaping. Some scenarios also explore mobile RIS nodes (e.g., B-6) and multi-RIS deployments (e.g., B-2), illustrating the need for flexible RIS control architectures. While three demonstrations use (or may use in the future) passive RIS panels, certain setups require more advanced RIS features, such as dynamic phase control, cooperative sensing functions, or programmable transformation of the impinging wavefronts. These RIS configurations play a crucial role in validating WP3 concepts on spatial signal manipulation, sensing enhancement, and robust localisation in cluttered environments.

3.4 Frequency Bands and Bandwidth

The mapping of contributions to hardware reveals that WP3 demonstrations operate across a wide frequency span, from 2.4 GHz for basic sensing tasks (A-1) up to millimetre wave (mmWave) bands around 28–30 GHz (A-2, A-3, A-4, B-2, C-2), consistent with FR2 hardware availability and the need for high spatial resolution. Bandwidth requirements are similarly diverse: many setups require wideband signals up to 400 MHz, while others rely on narrowband or kHz-scale bandwidths for synchronization-focused or beacon-based sensing. This range emphasizes the need for flexible RF front-ends capable of switching between narrow and wide bandwidths depending on the sensing or communication task.

3.5 Synchronization Requirements

Synchronisation needs vary significantly across WP3 and are closely tied to whether a contribution involves cooperation among distributed nodes. Many setups operate without strict synchronisation (e.g., A-1, A-4, B-1, B-5, C-2), which simplifies deployment and aligns with practical ISAC use cases where independent clocks are the norm. Other configurations require coarse timing alignment (A-2, A-3), often to support multi-antenna processing or RIS coordination. Scenarios that involve multiple BSs, UEs, or mobile RIS nodes (e.g., B-6, B-11, B-14) demand explicit synchronisation among distributed RX nodes, sometimes with shared timing references or periodic alignment signals. These varying requirements guide the selection of synchronisation mechanisms—from free-running clocks to wired or wireless timing distribution.

3.6 Passive and Dynamic Objects

The updated list indicates that many WP3 contributions incorporate passive objects, either as sensing targets, scatterers, or environmental elements. These range from static reflectors (e.g., A-2, B-14) to mobile or rotating passive objects used for dynamic sensing experiments (e.g., A-4, B-13). The presence of such objects necessitates radar-like processing pipelines and supports experiments on target detection, multi-target tracking, and environmental characterization. Several scenarios also involve multiple targets or unknown passive object configurations, requiring robust sensing algorithms and integration with complementary sensors such as cameras or inertia measurement units (IMUs) when needed. These object-rich setups challenge DISAC's ambition to handle complex, dynamic environments and to fuse multimodal information for cooperative situational awareness.

4 Integration of methods from WP3 and WP4

To support the implementation of the demonstrations, algorithmic methods and procedures developed under WP3 and WP4 will be applied. Algorithms performing sensing and communications, orchestration approaches for coordination of multiple devices and spectrum resources, as well as protocols exemplifying the architecture of WP2 will act in synergy to achieve quantitative targets. A number of technical contributions of the above WPs have been designed with

the scenarios, infrastructure, and objectives of the five different demos. Those have been described in the corresponding sections of each demo of this document and are further detailed and categorized hereafter. In addition to the per-demo mapping available in Section 2, in this section we summarize and categorize the broader integration of such demonstrators to the overall tasks and objectives of WP3 and WP4. Additionally, contributions and technical advancements from WP3 and WP4 that have a close relation to the demos are further discussed below. Relations of specific contributions to the relevant demos will be also included in the upcoming deliverables of the above work-packages, while the down-selection and implementation of such methods will be described in the next WP5 deliverable.

4.1 ISAC Methods from WP3

Waveform design approaches, addressed under Task 3.1, will take advantage of the equipment provided under Demos #1 and #3 to experimentally verify the theoretical and simulation results. Precisely, the channel sounder of Demo #1 will enable newly implemented ISAC waveforms to be precisely measured and their performance to be compared to standard waveforms under different sensing metrics and conditions. Demo #3 offers a testbed for comparing the novel semantic-based waveforms to traditional approaches, such as OFDM.

The 4x4 MIMO channel sounder of Demo #1 (Setup d) will provide high quality data to enable precise testing of ISAC channel estimation techniques. Under the various setups of Demo #1 (see [6GDISAC-D51] for further details), advanced MIMO architectures including RISs, hybrid reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (HRISs) [AAS+21], DMAs [IAS+21], and full-duplex may be evaluated. Demo #1 (Setup c), is particularly designed to generate HRIS data, which can be synthesized in a way that emulate DMA and full-duplex scenarios. Additionally, Demos #4 and #5 are precisely designed to test algorithms operating RISs for sensing. Algorithms addressing the synchronisation of multiple devices will leverage the high-precision time bases data provided by Demo #1 (particularly Setup d over large-scale mobile trajectories, and Setups a to c with limited covered areas) thanks to embedded rubidium clocks, but also the inherent synchronisation between the multiple ports of the VNA in other sounder Setups (a to c).

Moreover, digital-twin-based positioning and localisation may be achieved using the 5G PRS pilots offered by Demo #2. Handover mechanisms may further be evaluated on 5G BSs. Such 5G waveforms may further enable RF imaging approaches, once also combined with data from multiple RX positions of Demo #1 (Setup d). Sensing-aided communications, that incorporates user localisation can be evaluated directly in the near-field regime by exploiting moving target data of MIMO transceivers from Demo #1 (Setup d).

4.2 Protocol and Orchestration Approaches from WP4

The protocols developed under WP4 are intended to provide a roadmap for the operation of the devices involved in the demonstrations. Operational components include the initial access of the user to the system, the identification of devices, messaging exchange for control and data transfer. Protocols for distributed sensing of connected and non-connected targets have been designed in a way that can be applied to similar deployment scenarios as the ones in Demos #1 - #5. Protocols for RIS control are particularly useful for Demos #4, #5, as well as Demo #1 (Setup c). Protocols based on dynamic beam searching may leverage the directive antenna and beamforming capabilities of Demo #1 (Setups b and d). Semantic and target handover protocols complement the algorithms offered by WP3 in Demos #3 and #2, accordingly. Finally, protocols for federated learning are designed to take advantage of distributed setups that may be materialized from data derived from Demo #1 (Setup c).

The developed orchestration algorithms are designed to balance trade-offs between performance and system requirements and may then address problems regarding energy efficiency and frequency resource management. On that aspect, cooperative localisation schemes will be implemented based on the acquired data of Demo #1 (Setups a, b, and d), as well as Demo #4

for the integration of RISs. Such data may further be leveraged to demonstrate approaches related to detection of non-cooperative RISs and eavesdroppers. Federated learning schemes will capitalise on the developed protocols and may thus be applied to data collected from distributed devices for edge learning scenarios Demo #1 (Setup d). Finally, shared and fragmented spectrums may take advantage of high-bandwidth data of both the 5G base station of Demo #2 or the sounding of Demo #1, toward more economical sensing.

5 WP2 Architectural Components and Performance Indicators

5.1 6G-DISAC architecture and mapping to WP5

In this section, we firstly briefly recap the proposed 6G-DISAC architecture as detailed in [6GDISAC-D22], and we identify its main building blocks and interfaces that can be found within the demonstrators described in Section 2.

Figure 5-1: Preliminary 6G-DISAC architecture [6GDISAC-D22].

The 6G-DISAC architecture proposal, as depicted in Figure 5-1, relies on the following main entities:

- **SeMF:** the sensing management function, which is located in the core network and deals with sensing requests from services, discovery and selection of SRx and STx, negotiating data representations, configurations, etc.
- **Central SePF:** the central sensing processing function, which is located in the core network and takes care of collecting measurements from SRx or Edge/Local SePF and processing them according to the agreed data representation model.
- **Edge SePF:** intermediate SePF, that collects measurements from SRx and Local SePF.
- **Local SePF:** the lowest level of SePF, that pre-processes measurement data directly at the SRx and forwards the result to the Edge/Central SePF.
- **ST:** the sensing target is a device/object that is being sensed by a sensing service/application, which is passive and not connected to the network.

- **SRx:** an entity that receives the radio signal, which is used for a sensing service/application.
- **STx:** an entity that transmits the radio signal, which is used for a sensing service/application.

The above list of network entities is mapped to the demonstrators presented in Section 2 in Table 5-1 below.

Table 5-1: Mapping of DISAC architectural components onto demonstrators.

Demo#	SeMF	CSePF	LSePF	ST	SRx	STx
Demo #1	N.a.	N.a.	N.a.	Single	Multiple	Multiple
Demo #2	N.a.	Yes	No	Single	Single	Single
Demo #3	N.a.	No	Yes	No	Single	Single
Demo #4	N.a.	Yes	Multiple	Single	Multiple	Single
Demo #5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Multiple	Multiple	Multiple

The main architecture enablers are summarized as follows:

- **Data processing and data representation:** since the requirements of sensing applications may vary, it is essential to agree beforehand on the type of data representation and associated processing. Moreover, such agreement is dynamic as it varies with the underlying channel conditions and the involved network nodes, which may have different requirements and capabilities in terms of processing power, energy budget, etc.
- **Object tracking and handover support for passive targets:** the ability to localize and track passive objects (STs), which are not connected to the network. Since such objects may be, in general, mobile, this includes the handover of their tracking across multiple consecutive network entities.
- **Support for heterogeneous devices:** it refers to the capability of the DISAC environment to support a wide range of heterogeneous devices with varying communication (e.g., number of antennas) and computation capabilities, multi-modal sensors (e.g., LiDAR, cameras, acoustic radars, etc.), control and reconfigurability characteristics (e.g., static, reconfigurable or autonomous)
- **Semantic enablers:** by processing multi-modal sensor data intelligently, 6G-DISAC reduces data volume while enhancing context awareness and interoperability. As a result, the 6G-DISAC architecture supports semantic waveforms, semantic radio access network (RAN), semantic alignment, etc.

The following Table 5-2 maps the 6G-DISAC architecture enablers to the relevant demonstrators presented in Section 2.

Table 5-2: Mapping of DISAC architectural enablers to the demonstrators.

Enabler	Relevant Demo
Data processing and data representation	Demo #2
Object tracking and handover support for passive targets	Demo #5

Support for heterogeneous devices

Demo #1, Demo #4, Demo #5

Semantic enablers

Demo #3

5.2 6G-DISAC KPIs Mapping

In this section, we make an explicit connection between the 6G-DISAC KPIs, as detailed in [6GDISAC-D23], and the demonstrators presented in Section 2 of this deliverable. In particular, in Table 5-3 we identify the subset of 6G-DISAC KPIs, which are relevant and quantifiable in each demonstrator.

Table 5-3: Mapping of relevant DISAC KPIs.

KPI	Relevant Demos
Communication performance	Demo #1, Demo #2, Demo #4, Demo #5
User/target localisation accuracy	Demo #1, Demo #2, Demo #4, Demo #5
Target detection capability	Demo #2, Demo #5
Sensing resolution	Demo #1, Demo #4, Demo #5
Semantic accuracy	Demo #3
Spectral efficiency	Demo #2, Demo #3
Semantic efficiency	Demo #3

6 Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable D5.2 builds upon the previous D5.1 [6GDISAC-D51] by outlining the rationale behind the selection of components, technologies, and methodologies that will underpin the demonstrators of the 6G-DISAC framework. While D5.1 defined the architectural building blocks and interfaces, the work presented here identifies and justifies the technical approaches to be adopted in the upcoming proof-of-concept implementations and measurement activities.

By explicitly linking each demonstrator to the main technical methods developed in WP3 and WP4—following the specifications in [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41]—the deliverable ensures a coherent integration of algorithmic and system-level innovations. The selected demonstration use-cases align with those defined in WP2 [6GDISAC-D21], and their evaluation draws on the relevant KPIs established in [6GDISAC-D23]. Furthermore, this document has clarified the architectural elements involved in each demonstrator and their roles within the broader 6G-DISAC framework, as described in [6GDISAC-D22].

Looking ahead, the insights and technical choices consolidated in this deliverable lay the groundwork for the next development stages, providing a clear blueprint for implementing, testing, and validating the 6G-DISAC concepts in realistic scenarios, thereby advancing the project toward higher technology readiness. Indeed, the work of WP5 in the upcoming months will focus on deploying the selected demonstrators, collecting the associated results and measurements, and evaluating their overall performance as per the specified KPIs. Such results will then be

consolidated in the final phase of the project, extracting key outcomes and technical recommendations.

7 References

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